
**Promoting Good Governance via Model Gaon concept:
A Case study of Banda district**

Heera Lal¹

Abstract

Poverty stricken backward districts, also known as ‘aspirational districts’ are plagued with multiple challenges, where the common people are the worst sufferers. It is the responsibility of the elected representatives, administrative officers and staff to work in tandem with the people to enable the alleviation of such challenges. Model गाँव is one such initiative through which people’s aspirations to prosper and contribute to the holistic development of their villages were fulfilled. I highlight some of the steps taken by me in Banda district of Uttar Pradesh, during my tenure as the District Magistrate.

Keywords: Model गाँव, Good Governance, Banda District, Development

¹ Dr Heera Lal, an officer of the Indian Administrative Service (IAS) is Additional Mission Director, National Health Mission, Uttar Pradesh.
Email: heeralalias@gmail.com.

Bureaucrats and civil servants are often regarded as the changemakers of modern India. And with a plethora of social and policy problems that leave their trail, only few could perfect the job they have been assigned - to undo the unjustness and unfairness of these problems.

I would like to share a similar story from my work in Banda district where I served as the District Magistrate. I was leading the district which had been backward striven for ages, in the essential categories of water accessibility, public health and nutrition, education and women empowerment. The success of my work has now become the face and aspiration of many; in the form of creating development models for the rural India where they are led with practical and implementable approaches. With this vision of transforming Indian villages, he is now the Honorary Advisor to Model गाँव (translated into English as model village), a non-profit and a dream project of his, which educates and empowers villagers to holistic and sustainable development.

Figure 1: Map of Banda district, Uttar Pradesh

Source: Wikimedia Commons

Banda, being the best example as a case study of good governance, here are some of the policy interventions that were made:

Water Conservation

The district being plagued by water scarcity, I intervened by first introducing the drive Bhujal Bachao, Payjal Badhao (translated into English as enhance groundwater, protect drinking water). I took the initiative to build 2,605 contour trenches and held 469 jan choupals engaging around 35,000 villagers on water budgeting and groundwater recharge. Around 2,180 hand pumps were

installed and more than 250 wells across 470 Gram Panchayats recharged. My efforts resulted in the accumulation of at least 1 lakh kiloliters of water annually. These initiatives were supported by eminent organizations like WaterAid India and People's Science Institute, thus also putting Banda in the national and global map.

Adding on to my work methods of involving people as a means to meet solutions, that is, a participatory approach, I was associated with the Banda Water campaign, which was later acknowledged as being a prime example of community engagement model which involved water parliaments for groundwater recharge, rain water harvesting and mass awareness campaigns.

Public Health and Nutrition

I personally spearheaded awareness campaign initiatives to make understand the importance of Yoga and finally led the different pillars of the district be it public offices, schools, colleges, prisons and in both urban and rural places of the district into adopting Yoga. I led the foundation stone for a recreation based and health wellbeing park 'Oxygen Park' in the district. Malnutrition and child stunting seemed to be an aggravating issue not just for Banda district but for a large portion of rural population and is still a major health crisis in India despite efforts of Mid-Day Meal and POSHAN. I strategized the intervention with the help of UNICEF by starting 'Bal Poshan Satra' (child nutrition sessions) which involved live feeding demonstrations and counselling sessions for mothers. Cases of Severe Acute Malnutrition (SAM) were carefully examined and other efforts like growth monitoring and awareness about home cooked nutritious diet was also brought into place. It was a roaring success with more than 2000 undernourished children having fully recovered.

Women's Empowerment

Taking one step further in the Model Village concept, the involvement of women in the development of the economy of any district and state cannot be negated. Whether it is about self-employability, participation in sports and related activities, formal education, my efforts brought in huge success. I firmly believe that 'women empowerment is a necessity, not an option'.

Education

Realizing that education is the root cause of many of the social evils present, I led innovations in the education sector as well. 'Prerna' app was one of those initiatives which helped increase the enrollment of children at the primary level, decreased the early exit of children from school, and checked if the students were present. Teachers had to click photographs and send it via app to the administration as a proof for class presence. This revolutionary app was soon realized as a model for the rest of the state.

Environment

Realizing early the importance of environment protectionism and climate change, I did not back out from making efforts which included planting thousands of tree saplings and also initiated a phenomenon called 'Ped Prasad', where I used religious places - temples and mosque to cater to the larger audience and instilling behavioural change in them about the importance of the cause.

Other significant feats

In addition to all of the above, I have also led prison reforms where he engaged the inmates with various sports and recreation-based

activities and took a serious consideration of the physical and psychological health and well-being of the inmates present.

For the youth, I have initiated startup programs to elevate and accelerate employment rate in the district and what he referred to as ‘a much needed exposure’.

He restarted the local dairy industry and had it incorporated in the larger dairy market which also led to economic upliftment for many.

I also conceptualized a massive voter mobilization drive to strengthen the very foundation of a democracy - the election. His initiative increased voter turnout throughout the district and is one of the better figures in the entire country right now.

Challenges

Banda district has now evolved to be truly a model village for the rest of the state and the country. The upcoming revised datasets of Census, National Family Health Survey (NFHS), National Statistical Survey and Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Index will give a clearer, optimistic picture of the progress and will help fuel the development machinery running.

While the efforts and approaches at the legal, policy and administrative level may differ with the socio-political-cultural scenario of a place and also its topography; but the scope to reach for the higher in the most crucial of parameters is something to be endowed by the rest of the country.

The concept of replicating the idea of Model गाँव may not see the similar light of the day and will be full of hurdle and challenges –

Table 1: Challenges in replicating Model गाँव outside Banda district, Uttar Pradesh (in India)

Institutional	Challenges in the form of corruption, red tapism, mismanagement and inefficiency, lack of will, low skilled workers in the respective departments and lack of clear vision- both short term and long term, are some of the institutional lacunas one has to go through to make a change of some kind.
Social acceptance and Equity	<p>While the community participation approach has been applauded, it is also to be taken into consideration the inclusivity criteria and the social acceptance at large of other groups. Issues like caste, gender and religion invariably will play a hindrance factor in effectively deploying communities towards development.</p> <p>Besides this, failed behavioural changes methods and techniques will result in communities not being able to grasp or accept new policy changes. This may include interventions in sectors like environment, public health, water conservation, sanitation, digital modes of financial inclusion and most prominently, tabooed topics of sexual well-being, menstrual hygiene, female labour participation, etc.</p> <p>Concept of incorporating even the basic services like for example, separate toilets for women and girls in the schools (which in many blocks and districts of the country shockingly lack) have to be strategically brought about and making the population understand the importance of it will be a challenge.</p>
Effectiveness	<p>Policy interventions will also face the hurdle of how effective they can be on paper or after being implemented, how well monitored and effective they have been on ground.</p> <p>Policies, Laws and initiatives focused on the rural population should be evidence based and have a specific time period for trials. The lack of political will, political acceptance and aggravated political pressure also adds up to the ineffectiveness of a policy design.</p> <p>The feasibility of the methods also plays a key role from social dimension and the present administrative capacity.</p>

Source: Compiled by the author

Suggestions

The concept of ‘Model Village’ is in line and accordance of PM Adarsh Gram Yojana’s objective of social, cultural and economic development of a village and SDGs 3 (Good Health), 4 (Quality Education), 5 (Gender Equality), 6 (Clean Water), 10 (Reduced Inequality and Financial Inclusion), 11 (Sustainable Communities). Its nationwide implementation although ambitious is achievable for the present 718 districts of India. The hurdles and challenges can be best addressed and fought via intervening at the individual steps of any policy making.

Agenda Setting

The first step of policy making which involves brainstorming of ideas, suggestions, thinking of the problems at hand, different stakeholders to engage with stakeholders’ analysis, project initiation. This step should be able to incorporate the beneficiaries of any policy into discussion, along with other relevant stakeholders and hold continuous meetings and sessions before going forward.

Problem defining

The next crucial step is Problem defining which will involve boiling down to a precise problem, that is, a substantive one from a metaproblem. Problem defining will be important because it helps to figure what issues to deal with. It will be relevant in the sense that the policy to be discussed and implemented in the villages doesn’t go out of focus. A problem of lack of sanitation due to inefficiency in financial incentive should not be confused with lack of sanitation due to lack of adequate behaviour, as the

former is a problem of financial inclusion while the latter is a cultural and behavioural problem.

Discussing and choosing the 'best' alternative

The next step is laying out the best possible policy solutions that can aid in resolving the issue and problem in hand. With engagements and discussions and profiling out the best policy choice for any district, the next step is to choose out of the alternatives.

An adequate trial phase should be mandated in a certain number of blocks in the district to check for its efficacy and worth. Appropriate corrections should be initiated thereafter. Taking the example of sanitation again where people are yet to realize its benefits, a short 4-6 month trial period should be initiated to check if people are adopting the new toilets or specifically, what changes are required, like size, color, location inside the premise, etc.

Taking public and expert opinions and suggestions for the proposed alternative

The proposed policy alternative should be released in the larger context for the views and opinions of the public, civil society, think tanks, and other relevant experts to fill any loophole that is present or might arise after implementation.

Implementation

After review and series of discussions and changes, the policy is finally applied and implemented. Herein, the challenges of Institution lacunas, Social acceptance and equity, and Effectiveness, as discussed in the table above will come into play significantly and should be accordingly dealt with.

Monitoring and Review

Often an undermined and overlooked step, this is the most crucial because monitoring and review of any policy at work helps increase its efficiency and lays the path for better policies to be framed in the future. All the previous steps can be perfected depending on the importance given to this step of monitoring, reviewing, evaluating and rating a particular policy. As an example, a sanitation and toilet construction policy in a state can be well monitored by employing research professionals to visit different villages, discuss and interview Panchayat heads and Block-level officers, conduct focused group discussions, ground observations and report everything for analysis.

(The author would like to thank Indranuj Pathak for his valuable inputs.)